

PECULIARITIES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE PHONOLOGICAL SYSTEM

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Annotation: In the article special features of English phonology and main aspects of phonological system were analyzed. Every learners of English language knows that learning this language is much more difficult rather than other international languages according to the phonological side. The article discusses difficult points of phonology of English language.

Key words: *pair consisting, intricate way, production, perception, speech sounds, cataloging, phonemes, allophones.*

Language is a means to communicate, it is a semiotic system. By that we simply mean that it is a set of signs. Its A sign is a pair consisting—in the words of Ferdinand de Saussure—of a signifier and a signified. We prefer to call the signifier the exponent and the signified the meaning. For example, in English the string /dog/ is a signifier, and its signified is, say, doghood, or the set of all dogs. (I use the slashes to enclose concrete signifiers, in this case sequences of letters.) Sign systems are ubiquitous: clocks, road signs, pictograms—they all are parts of sign systems. Language differs from them only in its complexity. This explains why language signs have much more internal structure than ordinary signs. For notice that language allows to express virtually every thought that we have, and the number of signs that we can produce is literally endless. Although one may find it debatable whether or not language is actually infinite, it is clear that we are able to understand utterances that we have never heard before. In linguistics, language signs are constituted of four different levels, not just two: phonology, morphology, syntax and semantics. Today, we are going to talk about phonological features of English language.

Phonetics is the study of sounds. To understand the mechanics of human languages one has to understand the physiology of the human body. Letters represent sounds in a rather intricate

way. This has advantages and disadvantages. To represent sounds by letters in an accurate and uniform way the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) was created. We begin with phonology and phonetics. It is important to understand the difference between phonetics and phonology. Phonetics is the study of actual sounds of human languages, their production and their perception. It is relevant to linguistics for the simple reason that the sounds are the primary physical manifestation of language. Phonology on the other hand is the study of sound systems. The difference is roughly speaking this. There are countless different sounds we can make, but only some count as sounds of a language, say English[1].

The basic ideas of English phonetics and phonology, such as phonemes, allophones, syllables, weak forms, minimal pairs, contractions, intonation, stress, and pronunciation, will be covered in this session. [English](#) phonology is the system of speech sounds used in spoken English. Like many other languages, English has wide variation in [pronunciation](#), both [historically](#) and from [dialect to dialect](#). In general, however, the regional dialects of English share a largely similar (but not identical) [phonological](#) system. Among other things, most dialects have [vowel reduction](#) in [unstressed syllables](#) and a complex set of [phonological features](#) that distinguish [for tis and lenis consonants](#) ([stops](#), [affricates](#), and [fricatives](#)). Phonological analysis of English often concentrates on or uses, as a reference point, one or more of the [prestige](#) or [standard](#) accents, such as [Received Pronunciation](#) for [England](#), [General American](#) for the [United States](#), and [General Australian](#) for [Australia](#). Nevertheless, many other dialects of English are spoken, which have developed independently from these standardized accents, particularly regional dialects. Information about these standardized accents functions only as a limited guide to all of English phonology, which one can later expand upon once one becomes more familiar with some of the many other dialects of English that are spoken[2].

Phonetics is a method for accurately characterizing and cataloging linguistic sounds. By using phonetics, we can better understand aspects of language that we typically only hear in written form rather than in spoken form. Phonology is concerned with the ways that languages employ sounds to discriminate between different words. The characteristic sounds and patterns that are used in a particular language are referred to as phonological features. These characteristics of speech sounds include phonemes, allophones, syllables, intonation, stress, and other elements. For practice, the following is a list of phonological elements with examples:

These phonological features are essential for communication, pronunciation, and language comprehension[3]. It is possible to increase spoken fluency and phonetic accuracy by practicing these elements.

It is evident that the vocal chords play a major role in sounds (they are responsible for the distinction between voiced and unvoiced), and the sides of the tongue are also used (in sounds known as laterals). Table 3 gives some definitions of phonetic features in terms of articulators for consonants. Column labels here refer to what defines the place of articulation as opposed to the manner of articulation. The degree of constriction is roughly the distance of the active articulator to the passive articulator. The degree of constriction plays less of a role in consonants, though it does vary, say, between full contact [d] and ‘close encounter’ [z], and it certainly varies during the articulation (for example in affricates [dz] where the tongue retreats in a slower fashion than with [d]). The manner of articulation combines the degree of constriction together with the way it changes in time.

We know that English is difficult to learn because of its phonological system. It would be a lot simpler to pronounce English if the written form resembled the spoken form more closely. Amongst the most confusing bits are silent letters – r, l, b, h, k, n, p, s, t & w are all silent some of the time. Then there are letters that can be pronounced in lots of different ways – ‘s’ can be pronounced as /z/, ‘t’ can be pronounced in at least 5 ways, and an ‘n’ can become /m/ or /ŋ/. And that’s just consonants – English contains 19 vowel sounds, but it only has 5 vowels to spell them with, so who could possibly guess that ‘good’, ‘food’ and ‘blood’ all contain different vowel sounds (/ʊ/, /u:/ and /ʌ/)? English has 19 vowel sounds and 25 consonant sounds. Its vowel sounds cover the entire range of mouth positions – front, centre, back, open, close, spread, relaxed and rounded. Some vowels are long, others short, but all vowels change length depending on the level of stress on them. Many students speak languages with fewer vowels – a lot of modern languages (Spanish, Japanese, Arabic to name a few) have no more than 5 vowel sounds, for most learners, the 19 vowel sounds present an important area of study. Consonant sounds are also problematic – nearly everyone needs to learn the ‘th’ sounds /θ/ & /ð/, the approximant ‘r’ sound often requires attention, and other sounds such as /h/, /w/ and /ŋ/ cause a lot of errors. All students need to pay attention to accurate consonant production: voicing and placement need to be mastered.

Aside from the sounds of English, it is important to join everything together correctly. English has various ways of joining words: assimilation (2 sounds change each other), elision (one sound disappears), vowel + vowel joining (we add a /r/, /j/ or /w/ between the sounds) and consonant + vowel joining (a consonant joins the next syllable). Sometimes these are rather

bizarre – in the sentence ‘law and order’ only one /r/ would be pronounced – between ‘law_r_and’ – even though it is spelt with a ‘w’. The English are famous for saying one thing and meaning another – using intonation to show meaning. These subtleties can be lost on a learner of English. English uses a wide pitch range and four patterns – fall, fall-rise, rise & rise-fall. The rules of English stress are simple to learn, but impossible to see on the written page. If a learner of English is misunderstood, it is more often due to misplaced stress than incorrect pronunciation – for this reason stress is perhaps the most important aspect of clear speech.

To conclude all given facts above Although English is undeniably a very confusing and perhaps complicated language to pronounce well, there is some good news – it can be learnt. Pronunciation is like any other skill – it involves learning new movements and rules and practising them until they become second nature. Through studying the 4 key aspects of speech – sounds, structure, intonation & spelling rules, a student can take their English level to an entirely new level and with regular practice can alter their accent.

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